

**ECHOES OF TRADITION: FALCON IMAGERY IN
KARAKALPAK AND UZBEK VERSIONS OF ALPAMYS****Turdimuratova Abadan**PhD on Philological Sciences, Senior Lecturer of the Academy of the
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ABSTRACT

Both in the Karakalpak Ögiz jiraw version of the epic «Alpamys» and in Fazyl Yuldash's Uzbek version, lines that recur in other epics – traditional formulas and richly imagistic descriptions – appear frequently. In both versions the jiraws (bards) rely on traditional formulas while performing, singing with their own creative skill. For example, in the Ögiz jiraw variant, when Gülparşın and her mother Baysyn are leaving for Taishyhan's land and are saying farewell to their neighbors and childhood friends, they lament with lines such as:

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Lashyn edim, qanatimnan qayırıldım,

Jüyrek edim, doynağımnan mayırıldım. [6, p. 8] – and when Alpamys is imprisoned, Äshim sings to him:

Men jüriyppen doynağından mayırılğan,

Lashyn edim, qanatimnan qayırılğan. [6, p. 53] – telling of the humiliations he saw from Taishyhan.

Those same lines are repeated in the episode where Qultay baba meets Alpamys and also when Jädiger laments his orphanhood. In Fazyl Yuldash's version the lines appear as:

Uchqur edim qanotimdan qayrilib,

Yugruk edim tuyogimdan tayrilib...

or:

Uchqur eding, qanotingdan qayrilding,

Yugruk bolsang, tuyogingdan tayrilding...,

and occur in several places. [1, p. 29]

V. M. Zhirmunsky and H. T. Zarifov, describing the style of the people's epic in their book *Uzbek National Heroic Epic*, emphasize the importance of such lines: «Among the stable formulas of the Uzbek epic there are certain couplets which, even when they are not directly connected with the content in different plots and different epics, are nevertheless repeated». [5, p. 432]

Such repetitions usually appear across several couplets. In the examples above, in some lines the forms appear as «qayırıldım», «mayırıldım» or «qayrilding», «tayrilding», while in other places they reappear as «qayırılğan», «mayırılğan» or «qayrilib», «tayrilib». A. N. Veselovsky comments on such recurring refrains in epics: «A couplet is introduced by a certain situation or scene and then develops across paired lines. The opening of the following couplet returns us to that situation (with small changes) to the beginning of the first couplet, and that situation develops again, only a new detail or a stroke gently moves the event forward». [4, p. 76]

In the various epics where these refrains recur, the images of the falcon (lashyn) and the steed (tulpar) in the quoted lines carry symbolic meaning. Regarding these artistic repetitions in the Uzbek and Karakalpak versions of the epic, Prof. Q. Maksetov observes: «The images of suffering birds and horses express the hero's grief and misfortune». [7, p. 52] Thus he correctly interprets the symbolic meaning of the falcon and the swift horse.

The falcon symbol is historically and culturally bound to the steppe nomads' civilization. In Turkic mythology and epic tradition the falcon (and similar raptors) often have important symbolic significance: they signal power, freedom, and a connection with divinity. Falcons are associated with Tengri, the sky god, as a sign of the spirit's strength and the soul's ability to rise to the heavens. This symbolism is widespread in numerous Turkic epics and is deeply rooted in the nomadic and shamanic cultures of Turkic peoples.

G. N. Simakov points out that among the Turkic peoples of Central Asia and Kazakhstan, a falcon killed in battle or dying a natural death could be considered a material image of a warrior's spirit. Among the epithets that portray the heroic figure, «lashyn» and «burkit» (falcon and eagle) are specially emphasized. [10, pp. 64–65]

Indeed, the ancestors of the Turkic peoples in Central Asia and Kazakhstan lived a nomadic or semi-nomadic life and were engaged in hunting. In hunting, the falcon and the eagle played direct roles. «In the military and everyday life of the nomads, falcons and hunting played an important role. Nomads called 'Falcon and hunting – the mother of battle.'» [8, pp. 86–106]

T. A. Bernshtam also shows that in East Slavic folklore the falcon image has rich symbolic meaning. According to him, until the 19th century one of the falcon's functions was its association with wedding customs (the falcon as a wedding bird). «The falcon appears not as a lyrical but as a heroic image; at the same time it symbolizes love and fear. Its behavior has a martial character, which shows traces of a man's military organization». [3, pp. 30–31]

It is not accidental that the coat of arms of the Golden Horde formed by Turkic peoples features a double-headed bird. Even today the double-headed falcon or eagle appears as a symbol on the coats of arms of some Slavic countries (including the Russian Federation), which also carries historical meaning.

In the Alpomish epic (F. Yuldash variant) the falcon and the steed are called ushqur/uchqur (swift, soaring) and jüyrek/yugruk (fleet-footed). This can be regarded as part of the performer's individual stylistic skill. In fact, the falcon-like sapsan is considered the swiftest bird in ornithology. [9] Meanwhile, the horse is widely conceived in mythological notions as the most fleet and spirited animal.

It is also worth mentioning that archaeologists' surprise was caused by the Akshakhan city archaeological complex (located in the Beruniy district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan), where frescoes more than 2,300 years old were found remarkably well preserved. These wall fragments dated to the 3rd–2nd centuries BCE also depict kings wearing bird-like headdresses. [2] Thus the peoples of the Aral region from ancient times held wild birds in particular esteem.

From all this it follows that when the hero says «lashyn edim» («I was a falcon»), he declares himself once free, happy, and strong; the phrase «qanatimnan qayırıldıw» (having been torn from my wing) figuratively indicates that misfortune has overtaken him and that he is left in a weakened, miserable state

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